

A Framework for Applying Digital Technologies to Enhance Advance

Directives

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Covid-19 has made the possibility of serious illness and death more immediate for many. Increasingly, individuals recognize the importance of considering and declaring care preferences in the event of future incapacitating illness or serious injury [2]. Advance directives (AD) are one important means to do so; their primary aim is to increase the likelihood that patients' received care matches their preferred care. Despite AD's potential, however, research to demonstrate their impact has shown mixed results [2,10]. Managing care at the end-of-life is an important public health issue [9], and ADs in their current form may not be able to fulfil expectations regarding the delivery of person-centered, goal-concordant care.

While digital technology, such as apps, conversational agents, and immersive reality devices, are increasingly integrated into healthcare, and recent attention has been given to the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in clinical scenarios that depend on patient preferences [4], only a

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few pioneering efforts have been made to improve AD by means of digital technology [3,7]. Often, digitalization is limited to bringing online or in electronic form the static document itself. This is sometimes complemented with related text, such as educational booklets, embedded graphics, audio or video recordings, and links with answers to frequently asked questions [7].

A more thoughtful use of digital technology can help AD better contribute to facilitating respect for patient autonomy by supporting patient's ability to make informed choices based on their needs and values [8]. By harnessing existing digital technology capabilities to support the key elements necessary for decision-making capacity, *understanding*, *appreciation*, *reasoning* and *communication* [1], we can better actualize AD as tools that support fidelity to the patient since autonomy is predicated on informed decision making [6].

Understanding encompasses the ability to comprehend the components of the decision being made, and health literacy is a recognized barrier to engaging with AD [7]. Digital technologies can support understanding using real-time translation or subtitle generation of text, audio, and video material to teach users about the core terminology and concepts necessary to meaningfully consider the questions present in AD. The flexibility of how technology incorporates and presents information means that users can encounter what is pertinent to them and self-drive both the format and level of depth.

Appreciation, the ability to apply information to oneself and one's situation, is also essential for decision making, especially if the autonomy of the future self hinges on respecting the declared preferences of the present self, who is an imperfect surrogate due the challenge of projecting oneself into the future to anticipate preferred care as one's health status changes. To this means, digital technologies presenting videos, interactive thought experiments, personalized exercises with AI, and chat rooms with digital assistants can familiarize users not only with what

future scenarios and interventions might entail, but how they themselves might adapt and respond to those changing circumstances in ways previously not considered.

Digital technologies can support *reasoning*, i.e. the ability to negotiate the relevant aspects of decision-making coherently in the face of complex scenarios. Interactive content can introduce realistic situations that engage users in the exercise of considering various factors. AI algorithms can detect possible inconsistencies in the user's responses, and address these by prompting the user to further reflect, suggesting personalized content for clarification, or even offering recommendations. Moreover, immersive multiuser experiences with virtual or augmented reality involving a patient and surrogate or patient and doctor, can be used to determine congruence between the patient's preferences and other's interpretation of the AD. The AD and clinical reasoning based on it can be validated in this way and incongruences explored and addressed in real time.

Finally, when it comes to *communication*, the ability to express one's choices, AD are often not readily available or accessible when needed [7]. Digital technologies are well-suited to provide accessible storage and easy distribution [3]. Personalized reminders, such as those used in digital health interventions, can encourage completion, updating, and sharing of AD. Moreover, technology can grant access to AD by those authorized if the individual becomes incapacitated [7].

Despite potential, the use of digital technology to support informed decisions related to goal of care preferences has advantages and limitations that depend on the characteristics of its intended users and context of use. For example, conversational agents can address the challenge of upscaling AD due to a limited availability of physicians, resistance to talk with third parties about care choices, or lack of institutional resources. However, on-demand communication with a digital assistant replicating the role of a physician may not be appropriate for patients with

dementia or a serious illness, who, in turn, could benefit from the use of virtual reality devices in multiuser short sessions instead. AD should be living documents that “may change with time because of evolving preferences and clinical circumstances” [5]; technology should also be incorporated flexibly depending on the user, the disease trajectory, and the context, with the clear aim of supporting decisional capacity to promote the ultimate end of goal concordant care.

In summary, we believe the potential of digital technologies to enhance AD and support ACP is still not fully realized. The application of technology should be organized around an ethical framework of promoting informed decision making. To this end, we call for the involvement of healthy individuals, patients, physicians as well as researchers in human-computer interactions and biomedical ethics in the development of digitally enhanced AD.

References

- [1] P. S. Appelbaum and T. Grisso. 1988. Assessing Patients’ Capacities to Consent to Treatment. *N Engl J Med* 319, 25 (December 1988), 1635–1638. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJM198812223192504>
- [2] Catherine L. Auriemma, Scott D. Halpern, Jeremy M. Asch, Matthew Van Der Tuyn, and David A. Asch. 2020. Completion of Advance Directives and Documented Care Preferences During the Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Pandemic. *JAMA Network Open* 3, 7 (July 2020), e2015762. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.15762>
- [3] Nikola Biller-Andorno and Armin Biller. 2021. The Advance Care Compass- A New Mechanics for Digitally Transforming Advance Directives. *Front Digit Health* 3, (2021), 753747. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.3389/fdgth.2021.753747>
- [4] Nikola Biller-Andorno, Andrea Ferrario, Susanne Joebges, Tanja Krones, Federico Massini, Phyllis Barth, Georgios Arampatzis, and Michael Krauthammer. 2021. AI Support for Ethical Decision-Making Around Resuscitation: Proceed with Care. *Journal of Medical Ethics* (March 2021). DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1136/medethics-2020-106786>
- [5] Frank H. Bosch and David A. Fleming. 2015. Moving to High-Value Care: More Thoughtful Use of Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation. *Ann Intern Med* 162, 11 (June 2015), 790–791. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.7326/M15-0492>
- [6] Sophie Gloeckler, Tanja Krones, and Nikola Biller-Andorno. 2021. Advance Care Planning Evaluation: A Scoping Review of Best Research Practice. *BMJ Support Palliat Care* (October 2021), bmjspcare-2021-003193. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjspcare-2021-003193>

- [7] Michael J. Green and Benjamin H. Levi. 2012. The Era of “E”: The Use of New Technologies in Advance Care Planning. *Nurs Outlook* 60, 6 (2012), 376-383.e2. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2012.08.005>
- [8] Jaya K. Rao. 2015. Engaging Public Health in End-of-Life Issues: It Is Time to Step Up to the Plate. *Ann Intern Med* 162, 3 (February 2015), 230–231. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.7326/M14-2479>
- [9] Jaya K. Rao, Lynda A. Anderson, Feng-Chang Lin, and Jeffrey P. Laux. 2014. Completion of advance directives among U.S. consumers. *Am J Prev Med* 46, 1 (January 2014), 65–70. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2013.09.008>
- [10] Kuldeep N. Yadav, Nicole B. Gabler, Elizabeth Cooney, Saida Kent, Jennifer Kim, Nicole Herbst, Adjoa Mante, Scott D. Halpern, and Katherine R. Courtright. 2017. Approximately One In Three US Adults Completes Any Type Of Advance Directive For End-Of-Life Care. *Health Aff (Millwood)* 36, 7 (July 2017), 1244–1251. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1377/hlthaff.2017.0175>